

Fungi longevity on stored rice seeds

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The blotter technique was used to detect and identify sporulating fungi on 25 seeds each of 8 replications of indica varieties Siam 29 (IRGC acc. no. 5473) and Peta (IRGC acc. no. 3634) that had been stored 20 yr at 2 °C, 40% relative humidity, seed moisture content of 8-9%, in the medium-term storage room of IRGC. Seeds of both varieties were harvested in the 1968 dry season.

Nine fungal genera were detected (see

table). *Trichoconiella* and *Curvularia* were common on both varieties but *Fusarium*, *Drechslera*, and *Phyllosticta* were common only on Peta, perhaps because of genotypic differences.

Germination was 78.5% for Siam 29 and 45.5% for Peta. The greater abundance of fungi on Peta may have contributed to its lower germination.

The long-term survival of so many quiescent fungi may be a consequence of the cold, dry storage conditions. The presence of *Fusarium* sp., a genus that contains storage pathogens with short survival on seeds in storage, is surprising. Given the importance of long-term storage of germplasm in genebanks, the effect of fungi,

Genera of fungi detected on seeds of 2 rice varieties stored for 20 yr. IRGC, 1968 dry season.

Genus	Seeds infected (%)	
	Siam 29	Peta
<i>Trichoconiella</i>	72	62.5
<i>Curvularia</i>	11.5	25.0
<i>Phyllosticta</i>	0	23.5
<i>Drechslera</i>	0	14.5
<i>Fusarium</i>	0	10.0
<i>Pithomyces</i>	0	1
<i>Penicillium</i>	0	1
<i>Cladosporium</i>	0.5	0.5
<i>Rhizopus</i>	1	0

particularly seed pathogens, on the long-term viability and germination of aged seed warrants further investigation. □

CROP AND RESOURCE MANAGEMENT

Soils and soil characterization

Cultural practices to reduce iron toxicity in rice

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Fe toxicity in inland valley swamps drastically reduces rice yields. Two sets of experiments in 1984 and 1985 cropping seasons in the inland valley swamp at Magbolontor studied the influence of cultural practices on

reducing Fe toxicity and increasing grain yield.

Seedlings of different ages of Suakoko 8 (moderately tolerant of Fe toxicity) and Faro 15 (susceptible) were transplanted at 20, 30, and 40 d old in a randomized complete block design with 4 replications. Fertilizer was 60-40-40 kg NPK/ha. Toxicity symptoms were scored at early tillering and maximum tillering.

Symptoms were quite pronounced in Faro 15 at all seedling ages (Table 1).

Younger seedlings of Suakoko 8 were more tolerant than older seedlings.

Yields of Suakoko 8 were significantly higher than those of Faro 15.

Yields varied significantly between varieties and planting dates (Table 2). The results suggest that the optimal time of planting to escape serious Fe toxicity in the inland valley swamp at Magbolontor is during the first 2 wk of Jul. Planting earlier or later in the season significantly reduces yields, even in a tolerant variety. In Jul, the amount of water is too high to wash Fe off rapidly. □

Table 1. Effect of seedling age on Fe toxicity and grain yield. Sierra Leone, 1984-85.

Variety	Seedling age (d)	1984		1985	
		Grain yield (t/ha)	Toxicity (%)	Grain yield (t/ha)	Toxicity (%)
Suakoko 8	20	1.7	25	1.5	45
	30	2.4	25	1.9	40
	40	1.8	40	1.7	45
Faro 15	20	0.9	50	1.4	60
	30	1.0	50	1.9	55
	40	1.0	60	1.5	55
CV (%)		32.7		21.2	
LSD (0.05)		0.7		-	0.7

Table 2. Effect of planting date on Fe toxicity and grain yield. Sierra Leone, 1984-85.

	Suakoko 8		Faro 15	
	Yield (t/ha)	Toxicity (%)	Yield (t/ha)	Toxicity (%)
15 Jun 1984	1.5	30	1.2	60
15 Jun 1985	2.3	25	1.9	60
15 Jul 1984	2.4	30	1.4	60
15 Jul 1985	2.8	20	2.6	60
15 Aug 1984	1.3	45	1.1	65
15 Aug 1985	2.1	45	1.9	70
CV (%)	28.3	21.5		
F test				
Treatment	S	NS		
Dates	S	S		
LSD (0.05)	655 kg/ha			